

Research Article

Innovation in Glass

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Abstract: This article highlighted the public perception of using recycled waste glass for buildings is that it will be more expensive and may not be as effective as natural aggregates, but this perspective is changing thanks to increasingly advanced studies. This article examines recycled waste glass, standards, and long-term uses of waste glass as a building resource. The volume of created glass garbage will only increase as the world population grows, including an increase in the level of living. However, it is critical that we learn more about the utilization of recycled waste materials in construction, such as glass. The utilization of recycled waste materials in building construction is seen as a sustainable method of waste management and environmental preservation. Therefore, this paper will review the creativity and innovation in glass.

Keywords: Creativity; Innovation; Glass; Recycle; Waste

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1. INTRODUCTION

Several inventors highlighted the public perception of using recycled waste glass, they also state that glass can be recycled indefinitely with no loss of quality or value. Glass is a component of the solid waste stream, accounting for 8.7 percent of the waste stream in Nigeria. Between 80% and 85% of the total mass yield from the glass, the industry is either container from food, beverage, and pharmaceutical firms or flat glass for building development or vehicle production. They also discussed the source of glass wasted from various types of industries. Glass is reused in a variety of businesses across the world in various processes and as packaging material or for storing (Ogundairo, Adegoke, Akinwumi and Olofinnade, 2019).

2. METHOD SUMMARY

Furthermore, the uses of recycled waste glass as a construction material are discussed. The recycled waste glasses are included in the concrete either in crushed as an aggregate or in powder form in order to improvise the mechanical strength of the concrete. The type of glass powder and the colour has a great impact on the compressive strength and value of strength. However, studies have concluded that a mixture of 10% waste glass incorporated with somewhere between 15%-30% of concrete can result in fine aggregate which has no harmful consequences on the splitting tensile and the compressive strength. Waste glasses contains an enormous amount of calcium and silicon which is also called amorphous in nature. Hence it is said to be pozzolanic or even cementitious in nature.

Heavy-weight glass was thought to be a perfect suit as a fine aggregate as it expands fluidity unit volume when it is substituted. However, it is found that the compressive and flexural strength of recycled glass mortar gradually reduces as the heavy-weight glass is substituted in ratios.

The advanced stages of strength improvement of glass powder in concrete mixtures are great. It is suggested that the initial stages of the recycled waste glass powder should be done on a miniature scale. This will help the recycled waste glass powder to have a slower improvement in quality during the initial stages. The flexural strength of waste glass powder increases as it is used as a concrete aggregate.

Concrete splitting tensile strength is affected by the binder material and the size of the aggregate. When the expansion occurs, the tensile strength increases due to curing. The concrete properties can be influenced by many factors. Such as the way of handling glass powder, the source of the particle size, and the mineral composition of glass which leads to diverse reaction components with a binder in concrete. The workability is how easy the concrete is handled and gets decided how it will be shaped on the construction site. A slump test is used to test the workability of the concrete. At the batching point the slump test is carried out and while placing the concrete on the construction site. There was no huge contrast observed in the slump test while the glass powder is replaced by the mortar mixes (Tamanna, Mohamed Sutan, Lee, and Yakub).

An expansion was observed in a few tests due to the waste glass mixture having a low water absorption rate. Moving on to, the sustainable use of recycled waste glass.

- i. The green concrete innovations help in the betterment of the environment making use of recycled materials. There has been studies on the application of clay bricks powder and glass powder to be used in concrete. The glass powder is used to produce moderate strength concrete and the mix matrix substituted cement for clay.
- ii. Polymer concrete was created successfully and was also put in use. It was produced from worn-out glass waste lighting from the industries which use glass lighting elements. These glasses undergo a few processes before they can be used as aggregates.
- iii. The researcher As'ad Munawir evaluated the importance of the Alkali-Silica Reaction (ASR) phenomena in its engineering structures in a long run considering multiple ways glass waste is used in the form of either fine or course aggregate.

The steps involved in recycling discarded glass into useful materials such as ornamental aggregate, sand replacement, and pozzolanic additive for concrete manufacturing. The authors explain the process of Conversion waste glass to concrete which is from discarded waste glass to a partial cement replacement in concrete in detail.

Discarded waste glass is collected and sent to a processing facility for washing and crushing. The leftover glass is then sieved into 10 and 5 mm particle sizes for various applications. Waste glass with a particle size of 10 mm is commonly used as a natural aggregate replacement, whereas waste glass with a particle size of 5 mm is commonly utilized as a sand replacement in mortar. Finally, the microscopic particles are pulverized to produce glass powder with inherent strength, low water absorption, and the capacity to withstand high temperatures without deterioration. Ground glass powder with a particle size of 75-150 microns can be used as a pozzolan in concrete to replace cement. Better aesthetical concentration can be achieved by using different size of glass (Gowtham, Manikanda Prabhu, Gowtham, and Ramasubramani, 2021).

The inventors did mention about the physical qualities difference between glass and sand. When comparing the physical qualities of waste glass and sand, which are nearly identical in density,

specific gravity, and fineness modulus, waste glass as an aggregate replacement has an inherent benefit. Glass aggregate concrete will absorb less water than sand concrete, as glass absorbs 14% less water than sand. Waste glass can also be utilized as a concrete and paving block. Glass is pozzolanic or even cementitious in nature when finely powdered since it is amorphous and contains comparatively large amounts of silicon and calcium. When crushed to fine powder sizes, glass particles have been shown to be harmless in terms of alkali silica reaction (ASR) in concrete, which is absent in particle sizes below 100 μ m. This property makes it possible to employ waste glass in concrete building as a partial replacement for cement.

3. CONCLUSION

Authors emphasize that saving the earth is a global concern, and many stakeholders are looking for solutions to minimize energy use and reduce environmental effect. Research has found that glass is a sustainable building component. The enhancement in overall mechanical characteristic strength of concrete that had been advanced with recycled waste glass. Construction of buildings is a viable and profitable media to use repurposed glass waste Because 100% reliance on cement is unsustainable due to its high cost and waste glass can be reliance due to its sustainable due to its low emission of CO₂. The application of waste glass in construction also needs to be introduce as a guideline to others. Powdered glass particles have a high pozzolanic reactivity and can be utilized as a cement substitute. There will several benefits for environment and economic of recycling waste glass in Concrete Product which is reduce the waste disposal costs, the use of natural material in construction will be reduce and increase public awareness of the problem waste and the benefits of recycling.

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